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An Assessment of Women's Education in India

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Women's Education refers to any education that aims to improve the knowledge and intellectual and physical competence of female children and growing women. It includes school, college, and university level education and vocational, technical, professional, and health education. Indian Constitution guarantees equal rights and opportunities to both men and women alike. The all-around development of any Nation depends more on women folk. During British and Mogul rule in India, people kept their female children primarily for household work and family duties. They did not get opportunities like ancient women in the earliest period. Even now, we remember ladies like Sita, Savitree, Aamrpali, Gargi Maîteryei, and Bharti, wife of Mathili Scholar Mundan Mishra. Laxmi Bai, Savitri Rao Phule, and Jyotiba Phule, to name a few. They ardently advocated for the uplander of women in Society. In their Age, they raised their voices against the patriarchal dominance and gender discrimination. Instead, women folk were upressed, tortured, and physically assaulted by high-ups, British officers, Nawabs and Zamindars. Hence, no proper schooling was provided to female children. Before Common men, the burning problem was getting their female children married earlier in Life. This was the usual practice to avoid any sexual assault on women, and hence, education was provided only to male children because they were supposed to be the breadwinners for their families. The system of " Satti-Pratha" and Child marriage was in practice to provide safety to women. Promoting male-child education was the only option left to middle-class families and poor people in society; before 1947, only a few fortunate families could provide educational facilities to their daughters. They have full opportunities to study at the university level and even visit foreign countries for higher education. The leading striking causes of negligence and denial of Educational opportunities to women are Poverty, Superstitions in Society, the Lavish Life of British officials and so-called Nawabs and Zamindars, the Caste System, and Honour Killing in many high Families of Rajasthan, like many states. But during the past fifty years, a great Transformation in People's outlook has been seen. More significantly, women have come to the forefront of different walks of life in India. Modi's slogans " Beti Bachao and Beti Padhao are the prime motivation of modern Indian Society. This article contains secondary data for collecting information; the necessary secondary data is based on different research work, Journals, magazines, and newspapers.

Keywords: Asesement, Opportunities, Physical Assult, Satti – Pratha.

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Introduction

India is a celebrated nation in many ways in the world. 'Education' is a meaningful word for both educated and uneducated people. Teachers called 'gurus' are shapers of a student's life. In the past, Nalanda and universities were in the Ancient Period, where students from other countries came to get higher education. There were rich libraries, and many books were in manuscripts, Vedas, Purans, and Upanishad. Even now, the Gita Granth is recognised worldwide not for its religious value but for its highest educational value. It imparts moral education, diplomacy, war strategy, war diversity, and many more things. Since immemorial days, in Indian villages and temples, the deities of knowledge, Maa Saraswati, have been worshipped throughout the year. Both literate and illiterate men and women worship. Maa Saraswati, Maa Laxmi and Maa Durga form the 'Trinity - the supreme Power in the Cosmos.

In our Country, Teachers' Day is celebrated by all students, from the lowest standard to the highest level of Educational Institutes. Teachers are called 'Gurus'. Here, a Guru teaches books and provides every opportunity to develop physical, mental, spiritual, and ethical abilities.

All followers of any Sanatan Dharma celebrate "Guru-Purnima" with complete sincerity and devotion to their respective Guru, their Teacher. Maa Saraswati is a female goddess. These things of Indian life and society prove the superiority of women over men.

The present scenario is a changed world where, in almost all university exams or competitive exams, girls dominate boys. Even in IAS Exams, Girls have been Toppers. In the field of Civil administration, women have been chief Secretary of the state (Like Shusma Sahu, as chief secretary in

Jharkhand State when it came into existence) Smt. Indira Gandhi became India's most powerful Prime Minister and ruled for more than eleven years. Women had occupied the most honourable posts as presidents of India, Mrs. Pratibha Patil, Mrs. Meera Kumar, and speaker of Lok Sabha, even in the Army and Air Force. Navy women are being recruited as regular army personnel. They have attained the rank of Major General in the Army. The first woman pilot in the Indian Air Force was a Bihar, Bhavana. The world President of Om Shanti HQ at Mount Abu Prajapita Brahma Kumara Ishwariya Vishwavidyalaya is 93 years old, Maa Janki Devi. The Chief of Rikhiya Peeth of Yoga Centre is Smt. Satysangi, disciple of Swami Satyanand. For the first time in India, Bihar made 50% reservations for women in Panchayat Elections that continue. In short, today, women are in dominating positions and enjoy complete liberty in all walks of life.

Research Methodology

The present paper attempts to assess and analyse the various issues and challenges related to the ups and downs in women's societal positions and educational abilities in ancient and modern times. The data used is purely from Secondary Sources, per the study's needs.

Objectives of the study

The prime objective of this study is to examine women's education in India and the literacy rate of women in modern times. Another aspect is related to the position of contemporary women in Families, Educational Institutes, working-class young and grown ladies in sports offices, the Film Industry and the Field of Politics of the State and Centre. Hence, it might be summed up in the following points of consideration.

- To assess Women's Education Progress since the Independence of the Country.
- To identify the issues related to problems

women faced before getting higher education, especially medical education and technical learning in computer science, T.V. media, and the press. Difference between Govt. and Non. Govt. Jobs , Salary , burden of work , safety and security .

- Government schemes to promote Education for girls. For example, the Bihar Government has awarded cash payments of 10, 20, and 25 thousand rupees to unmarried girls who pass matriculation, graduation, and postgraduate exams. They get free education.
- Constitutional Provisions for Protection of Women's Honour, Abolishment of "Talak – System," laws against ragging in Educational Institutes when they are freshers.
- A Comparative study of modern women with women of the Vedic Period reveals that during the Vedic period and the post-Vedic period, Women had access to Educational facilities and other rights, like marrying a chosen life Partner in ' Swayamvara.'

The Situation of Women's Education in India

In the Vedic period, women had access to education in India, but they gradually lost this right in the British Period. There was a revival of interest in women's Education in India. During this period, various socio-religious movements in India. During this period, various socio-religious movements led by eminent persons like Raja Ram Mohan Roy and Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar emphasized women's Education in India. However, women's Education got a fillip after the country gained independence in 1947, and the government has taken various measures to provide education to all Indian Women.

The government has introduced several assistance initiatives in India to encourage women's Education. Here are a few of them:-

- Beti Padhao and Beti Bachao
- Sukanya Samridhi
- Mahila-e-haat
- Puraskar to Nari Shakti etc.

Issues and Problems of Women's Education in India

It is a matter of satisfaction that women's literacy rate has now reached 70.3%. Meanwhile, men's literacy rate is nearly 84 %. Many facilities have been created for women to promote higher learning, but a few obstacles are coming.

- Woman harassment in the Society
- Gender Discrimination
- Raggings of newcomer students by Senior Ones. Victims are both boys and Girls.
- Marriage Problem Owing to dowry system

Suggestions for meeting the Challenges:

- Most importantly, parents' attitudes need to change. Parents need to realise that investing money in girls' education is equally beneficial as investing money in boys' education.
- Financial support should be provided for girls' education from primary to higher secondary levels.
- Female teachers must be fully available in government schools and colleges.
- Encouraging married women to take up at least part-time teaching in village schools, working as school mothers, and providing special incentives for teachers.
- Providing Gender and comprehensive sexuality education in schools.
- Modi's slogans 'Beti Bachao' and 'Beti Padhao' have created a congenial atmosphere for encouraging female

education. Govt's. The decision to give 'Right to the free entrance in the school of all poor and downtrodden of the society.

- Abolishing the 'Talaq' system has encouraged Muslim girls to march ahead in different walks of life.

Constitutional provisions for women

The Indian constitution specifies provisions for education in the following significant areas of education:-

Provisions	Article
Education for Women	15(1),(3)
Equality for opportunity	16
Right to Education	21(A)
Religious Education	25,28(1),(2),(3)
Education of Minorities, protection of interests of minorities	29
Right of Free and Compulsory Education	45
Fundamental duty to provide the opportunity for Education	51(A)
Education in Union Territories	239
Instruction in the mother tongue at the Primary Stage	350(A)
Promotion of Hindi	351

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that women's education is equally important as men's education for the

development of any nation. The Future of Women's Education is bright in India. A female university like the one in Rajasthan, Banasthali Vidyapith, is a landmark in developing women's personalities. Women now feel strengthened and inspired to move ahead. Jawaharlal Nehru once said, ' Education a boy is educating a person or educating a girl is educating a nation.'

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